

Design and Optimization of Parity Generator and Parity Checker Based on Quantum-dot Cellular Automata

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Abstract : Quantum-dot Cellular Automata (QCA) is one of the most substitute emerging nanotechnology for electronic circuits, because of lower power consumption, higher speed and smaller size in comparison with CMOS technology. The basic devices, a Quantum-dot cell can be used to implement logic gates and wires. As it is the fundamental building block on nanotechnology circuits. By applying XOR gate the hardware requirements for a QCA circuit can be decrease and circuits can be simpler in terms of level, delay and cell count. This article present a modest approach for implementing novel optimized XOR gate, which can be applied to design many variants of complex QCA circuits. Proposed XOR gate is simple in structure and powerful in terms of implementing any digital circuits. In order to verify the functionality of the proposed design some complex implementation of parity generator and parity checker circuits are proposed and simulating by QCADesigner tool and compare with some most recent design. Simulation results and physical relations confirm its usefulness in implementing every digital circuit.

Keywords : Quantum-dot Cellular Automata (QCA), CMOS technology, logic gates, QCADesigner, clock.

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